

EU kNowleDge hUb foR enAbling MolteN Salt ReaCtor safety development and dEployment

D1.2 R&D needs for MSR development

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Authors	S. Lorenzi, E. Merle, N. Girault, Y. Gorse, J.M. Hamy, B. Hombourger, E. Klinkby, J. Krepel, P. Rubiolo, A. Smith
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Authors:	S. Lorenzi, E. Merle, N. Girault, Y. Gorse, J.M. Hamy, B. Hombourger, E. Klinkby, J. Krepel, P. Rubiolo, A. Smith
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Executive Summary

The objective of deliverable 1.2 is to identify some R&D needs related to the critical technology elements selected in the project with application on MSR design, safety and operation. WP leaders (ASNR, CNRS, Framatome, PSI, TU Delft) provided the status and the perspective on their specific area and collected the results of the identification to be applied in their respective WPs. Finally, Naarea, Saltfoss Energy and Stellaria as designers involved in the project contributed to share their view on R&D needs.

Keywords

R&D needs, Molten Salt Reactors

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1 Introduction

This report aims at drawing up a “list of R&D needs” related to the ENDURANCE project. For each WP, a list of Research & Development (R&D) needs is described along with the activities proposed within ENDURANCE project. Additional information on the MSR systems to be analyzed – based on the information on D1.1 “Review of the MSR designs” - are also provided. This report is based on Milestone 2 “Preliminary list of R&D needs”, written under the supervision of PoliMi, then the preliminary list has been reviewed and validated by the project's design partners.

2 R&D list

2.1 WP2 “Chemistry of fuel salt and structural materials in reactor environment”

The development of models and simulation codes of the chemistry of irradiated fuel salt on the one hand, and of corrosion mechanisms of structural materials on the other hand, is essential for the safety assessment of the MSR and its licensing process. Two main R&D needs have been identified in this context:

- **R&D need 1:** to increase the level of confidence on the thermo-physical data and correlations of the fuel salt and to establish good practices for the qualification process of the salt materials.
- **R&D need 2:** to evaluate the impact of the Fission Products (FPs) on the thermo-physical properties and analyse the effect of mechanical stress and irradiation on corrosion.

Table 1 summarizes the WP2 activities to be performed within ENDURANCE and the MSR systems to be analysed, organized according to the identified R&D needs.

Table 1. R&D needs identified, activities to be performed and MSR systems to be analysed within WP2.

R&D need	Activities to be performed in ENDURANCE	MSR systems to be analyzed	Concepts that can take advantage of the activities
2.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization of Round Robin on thermo-physical properties measurements • Density/viscosity measurements and simulations • Molecular dynamics modelling 	Nuclear fuel salt	All (generic research both for chloride and fluoride salts)
2.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Density/viscosity measurements and simulations • Molecular dynamics modelling • Combined corrosion and mechanical test • Post irradiation examinations of the SALIENT-03 irradiation campaign 	Nuclear fuel salt and structural materials	All (generic research both for chloride and fluoride salts)

2.2 WP3 “Experimental evidence on safety-related phenomena”

All the EU MSR designs have to fulfil the safety functions with a high degree of reliability. This may involve the use of passive features and considering the peculiar features of the use of liquid fuel. Two main R&D needs have been identified in this context:

- **R&D need 1:** to collect new experimental data on relevant phenomena that are inherent to molten salt coolants and have an important impact on the design and safety performances of MSRs.
- **R&D need 2:** to improve the current understanding on safety-related phenomena and to provide recommendations for the MSR design

Table 2 summarizes the WP3 activities to be performed within ENDURANCE and the MSR systems to be analysed, organized according to the identified R&D needs.

Table 2. R&D needs identified, activities to be performed and MSR systems to be analysed within WP3.

R&D need	Activities to be performed in ENDURANCE	MSR systems to be analyzed	Concepts that can take advantage of the activities
3.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment on deposition and interaction between particles and noble gas bubbles • Reactor experiments on criticality with fluorinated compounds • Experiment on natural circulation flow in advanced configurations (geometry, flow conditions, turbulent regimes) 	Fuel circuit, structural material, intermediate circuit	All reactors using coolant/decay heat removal systems similar to the one employed in the experiment but also other design could benefit from the improved current understanding
3.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiments mentioned for R&D need 3.1 • Modelling on solid particles transport and deposition • Validation of stability analysis methodology for natural circulation 	Passive DHRS, Fuel circuit, intermediate circuit	All

2.3 WP4 “Modelling preparedness for safety and licensing”

Molten salt designs are required to comply with the current and future safety regulatory environment, which includes recognized and shared practices and high-level standards. In this view, the evaluation and the enhancement of the predictive capabilities of modelling tools is a fundamental aspect. Two main R&D needs have been identified in this context:

- **R&D need 1:** to identify and categorize key phenomena and parameters for modelling and simulation with the assessment of their precision to fulfil given requirements
- **R&D need 2:** to prove the feasibility of computational chains to support the safety assessment of MSR design

Table 3 summarizes the WP4 activities to be performed within ENDURANCE and the MSR systems to be analysed, organized according to the identified R&D needs.

Table 3. R&D needs identified, activities to be performed and MSR systems to be analysed within WP4.

R&D need	Activities to be performed in ENDURANCE	MSR systems to be analyzed	Concepts that can take advantage of the activities
4.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elaboration of a “non-traditional” PIRT on three different accident families • Establishment of Target Accuracy requirements for simulations and parameters with respects to safety assessment procedures and regulatory requests 	Entire reactor, in particular ARAMIS-P will be taken as representative case (small chloride breeder loop-type)	Larger homogeneous pool type reactor in chloride/fluoride fast reactor could benefit from the activities. In general, any other type of MSR core-design sharing common phenomena identified in the PIRT
4.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation of BEPU methodology for MSR safety assessment based on Hi2Lo representations • Application of Hi2Lo representations to selected transients & assessment of high-fidelity models through code-to-code comparisons • Derivation of specific correlations to be implemented in system codes (CFD- informed extension of system codes) • Development of non-intrusive methods for internal assessment of uncertainties in selected computational chains for BEPU calculations • Verification/validation of the improved chains/tools for natural convection phenomena through the performance of experimental-based benchmarks 	Entire reactor, in particular ARAMIS-P will be taken as representative case (small chloride breeder loop-type)	Larger homogeneous pool type reactor in chloride/fluoride fast reactor with potential 3D TH effects

WP5 “Sustainability and safeguards compliance of MSR fuel cycle”

Sustainability is a key feature for the advanced systems and even more for MSRs due to their flexibility in the fuel cycle and the liquid nature. For the same reasons, safeguards compliance of MSR systems should be evaluated to ensure the deployment of these systems. Two main R&D needs have been identified in this context:

- **R&D need 1:** to evaluate different MSR concepts from a social and environmental sustainability perspective, considering different salt clean up and reprocessing techniques
- **R&D need 2:** to evaluate the proliferation resistance and safeguardability of different fuel cycle options and reprocessing schemes

Table 4 summarizes the WP5 activities to be performed within ENDURANCE and the MSR systems to be analysed, organized according to the identified R&D needs.

Table 4. R&D needs identified, activities to be performed and MSR systems to be analysed within WP5.

R&D need	Activities to be performed in ENDURANCE	MSR systems to be analyzed	Concepts that can take advantage of the activities
5.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized methodology for the assessment of MSR fuel cycle sustainability • Evaluation of nuclear flows and source term distribution in different MSR concepts • Salt reprocessing techniques review • Analysis of out-core passive off-gas system • Salts retention capability during nominal and accidental conditions 	Fuel core, fuel treatment unit and reprocessing. According to available data and considering evaluated assumptions, different concepts will be studied	All, no specific limitation to a type of reactor
5.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salt reprocessing techniques review • Preliminary safeguardability evaluation of the MSR concepts, and fuel waste and reprocessing systems 	Entire reactor. According to available data and considering evaluated assumptions, different concepts will be studied	All, no specific limitation to a type of reactor

2.4 WP6 “Demonstration of safe MSR adaptability in future decarbonized energy scenario”

New challenges and opportunity are brought by the decarbonization challenges in the energy field for which advanced systems need to be ready. Two main R&D needs have been identified in this context:

- **R&D need 1:** to clarify the status of the MSR technology regarding flexibility and the non-electrical application, identifying its poly-generation capabilities;
- **R&D need 2:** to identify potential safety concerns related to the flexibility and provide associated recommendations to secure the future licensing of such concepts.

Table 5 summarizes the WP6 activities to be performed within ENDURANCE and the MSR systems to be analysed, organized according to the identified R&D needs.

Table 5. R&D needs identified, activities to be performed and MSR systems to be analysed within WP6.

R&D need	Activities to be performed in ENDURANCE	MSR systems to be analyzed	Concepts that can take advantage of the activities
6.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a trade study on the flexible use of the MSRs. • Definition of MSR plant configurations and energy conversion systems for non-electrical end uses • Development of multiphysics and system-level tools to evaluate the poly-generation configurations in MSRs 	Entire reactor. According to available data and considering evaluated assumptions, different concepts will be studied	All, no specific limitation to a type of reactor
6.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of multiphysics and system-level tools to evaluate the poly-generation configurations in MSRs • Identification of potential safety concerns of poly-generation use. 	Entire reactor. According to available data and considering evaluated assumptions, different concepts will be studied	All, no specific limitation to a type of reactor

3 Conclusion

This deliverable provides an overview of the main R&D needs identified within the ENDURANCE project, with reference to the different activities and MSR systems considered. For each WP, the proposed activities have been mapped to the corresponding R&D needs. The analysis highlights how the activities planned within ENDURANCE contribute to the maturation of critical technological elements supporting the development and deployment of Molten Salt Reactor technology.

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